

Specific psychological skills of Indian male badminton players at different levels of achievement

Dr Priyanka Yadav¹ and Dr Parvez Shamim²

¹Associate Professor, Department of Physical Education Mihir Bhoj P. G. College, Dadri, G.B. Nagar

²Assistant Professor, Department of Physical Education Govt Degree College Budaun

Abstract

The purpose of the study was to assess specific psychological skills of Indian male badminton players of different levels of achievement i.e., International, Senior, Junior and Sub- Junior National. The sample of the present study comprised of 173 male Badminton players of India. Keeping in view the objectives, the players were categorized into four main groups: International (N=26), Senior national (N=33), Junior national (N=56) and Sub-junior national (N=58). The questionnaire was administered to the four sample groups- international, senior, junior and sub- junior male Badminton players. To assess the specific psychological skills of International, Senior, Junior and Sub-Junior National Badminton players of India, questionnaire Athletic Coping Skills Inventory –28 (ACSI-28) prepared by Smith et.al was administered, Means and Standard Deviations were computed. One – way analysis of variance (F-ratio) was computed to find out the significant difference among means of Specific Psychological Skills and its sub-factors of International, Senior, Junior and Sub-Junior National badminton players. This was followed by application of Scheffe's Test of post-hoc comparisons to determine the significant differences between ordered-paired means. The level of significance was set at 0.05. There was a significant difference in the international, senior, junior and sub-junior national male badminton players on confidence and achievement motivation, as the obtained F-value of 3.164 is greater than the tabulated $F_{0.05}(169,3) = 2.658$. As the F-ratio was found to be significant Scheffe's Test of Post-Hoc comparisons was applied to study the significance of difference between international, senior, junior and sub- junior National male badminton players. there was no significant difference among international, senior, junior and sub-junior national men/boys badminton players on confidence and achievement motivation as the obtained mean differences were less than respective critical differences.

Therefore, it can be concluded: International badminton players had higher mean values than senior, junior and sub-junior national in specific psychological skills. Significant differences were found in confidence and achievement motivation among international and junior national, international and sub-junior national, senior and sub-junior national male badminton players.

Keywords: badminton player, confidence level, achievement motivation

Introduction

By nature, human beings are competitive and ambitious for the excellence in all athletic performance. Not only every man but every nation wants to show their supremacy by challenging the other nation. Thus, this challenge stimulates inspires and motivates all the nations to sweat and strive to run faster jump higher and throw longer in present competitive sports world. This can only be possible through scientific systematic and planned sports training as well as canalizing them into appropriate games and sports by finding out their potentialities.

A traditional belief in sports world and especially in physical education is that the only way to learn a motor skill is spend long hard hours physically practicing. But here are many other (non-practice) strategies to be utilized to enhance human motor performance. Reading about a skill,

watching a video, talking with the coach, or just mentally stimulating the movements to be executed may also be effective strategies enhancement. These strategies involve some type of cognitive processing and many may be mediated by the formation of images or verbal labels. It is built up during long periods of training sessions. To realize a top performance in sports with physiological and psychological components, body and mind have to form a unit i.e., the top level of performance sports persons should possess the optimum level of psychological skills along with physical and physiological aspects according to the nature of the sports.

All sport and exercise participants fall victim to mental let down and mistakes conversely, most sport performers also know what it feels like to be “in the zone”, where everything seems to come together effortlessly and performance is exceptional. Mental and emotional components often overshadow and transcend the purely physical and technical aspects of performance. In any sport a player’s success (or failure) results from a combination of physical (e.g. Strength, speed, balance, co-ordination) and mental (e.g., concentrations, confidence, anxiety management) abilities. Most coaches consider that sport is at least 50% mental range.

It is a misconception that some people enter the world equipped with mental skills that champions are born rather than made. Yes, we are all born with certain physical and psychological predispositions, but skills can be learned and developed, depending on the experiences we encounter in our lives. No great athlete ever achieved stardom without endless hours of practice, having and refining physical skills and techniques. Although some athletes do possess exceptional physical skills, they had to work hard to develop their talents to become champions staying calm under pressure, maintaining concentration despite distraction and keeping confident in the face of failure are simply not innate. Rather they are skills (specific psychological skills) that need systematic practice and integration with physical skills.

The purpose of the study was to assess specific psychological skills of Indian male badminton players of different levels of achievement i.e. International, Senior, Junior and Sub- Junior National.

Methodology

The sample of the present study comprised of 173 male Badminton players of India. Keeping in view the objectives, the players were categorized into four main groups: International (N=26), Senior national (N=33), Junior national (N=56) and Sub-junior national (N=58)

The sample representing the International and Senior National badminton players consisted of those players who participated in the Senior National Badminton Championship, held at Jemshedpur, Jharkhand from 31st January to 6th February 2005. The sample representing the Junior and Sub -Junior National consisted of those players who participated in Junior National Badminton Championship, held at Panjim, Goa from 31st October to 8th November 2004, and Sub -Junior National Badminton Championship, held at Chandigarh, from 10th October to 16th October 2004 respectively.

The age for junior and sub-junior was under 19 and 16 years respectively. Their eligibility was determined on the basis of the reference date i.e., date of the commencement of the tournament (qualifying, if applicable). Hence the reference date of the junior and sub-junior national badminton championship was 1st July as determined by Badminton Association of India- competition regulations. However, the player’s level of achievement was decided on the basis of the highest level of tournament he/she played in national championships. International badminton players were those who represented the country in any international competition.

The questionnaire Athletic Coping Skills Inventory -28 (ACSI-28) prepared by Smith et.al contains 28 items on seven sports specific sub-scales: Coping with Adversity, Peaking Under Pressure, Goal Setting /Mental Preparation, Concentration, Freedom from Worry, Confidence and Achievement Motivation and Coachability. Each sport specific sub-scale contains four items. Responses obtained from the subjects on each statement of ACSI-28 questionnaire were recorded for analysis of data.

The questionnaire was administered to the four sample groups- international, senior, junior and sub- junior male Badminton players. The managers of all the teams were contacted personally and requested to permit their respective team members to serve as subjects for this study. Subjects were contacted personally when they were not busy and their sincere co-operation was solicited.

To assess the specific psychological skills of International, Senior, Junior and Sub-Junior National Badminton players of India Means and Standard Deviations were computed.

One – way analysis of variance (F-ratio) was computed to find out the significant difference among means of Specific Psychological Skills and its sub-factors of International, Senior, Junior and Sub-Junior National badminton players. This was followed by application of Scheffe’s Test of post-hoc comparisons to determine the significant differences between ordered-paired means. The level of significance was set at 0.05.

Results and findings

TABLE-1
MEANS AND STANDARD DEVIATIONS OF MEN BADMINTON PLAYERS ON CONFIDENCE AND ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION

S.No.	level of Achievement	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
1.	International	26	8.038	2.323
2.	National	33	8.485	2.138
3.	Junior National	56	8.375	2.277
4.	Sub- Junior National	58	7.293	2.991

TABLE-2
ANALYSIS OF VARIANCE OF INTERNATIONAL, SENIOR, JUNIOR AND SUB-JUNIOR NATIONAL MALE BADMINTON PLAYERS ON CONFIDENCE AND ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION

Source of Variance	DF	Sum of Squares	Mean Sum of Squares	F – ratio	tab F
Between Groups	3	57.199	19.066	3.164*	2.658
Within Groups	169	1018.5	6.027		
Total	172	1075.699			

* Significant at 0.05 level
tab F_{.05} (169, 3) = 2.658

It is evident from Table-2 that there was a significant difference in the international, senior, junior and sub-junior national male badminton players on confidence and achievement motivation, as the obtained F-value of 3.164 is greater than the tabulated $F_{0.05}(169,3) = 2.658$.

As the F-ratio was found to be significant Scheffe’s Test of Post-Hoc comparisons was applied to study the significance of difference between international, senior, junior and sub- junior National male badminton players and the data pertaining to this has been presented in Table- 3.

TABLE-3
SIGNIFICANCE OF DIFFERENCE BETWEEN THE ORDERED PAIRED MEANS ON CONFIDENCE AND ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION AMONG INTERNATIONAL, SENIOR, JUNIOR AND SUB-JUNIOR NATIONAL MALE BADMINTON PLAYERS

S.No.	Mean Scores				Mean Differences	Critical Difference
	INT.	SN	JN	SJN		
1.	8.73	8.49	-	-	0.24	1.81
2.	8.73	-	8.38	-	0.35	1.64
3.	8.73	-	-	7.29	1.44	1.63
4.	-	8.49	8.38	-	0.11	1.52
5.	-	8.49	-	7.29	0.20	1.50
6.	-	-	8.38	7.29	1.09	1.30

*Significant at 0.05 level

It is obvious from Table-3 that there was no significant difference among international, senior, junior and sub-junior national men/boys badminton players on confidence and achievement motivation as the obtained mean differences were less than respective critical differences.

Therefore, it can be concluded:

- International badminton players had higher mean values than senior, junior and sub-junior national in specific psychological skills.
- Significant differences were found in confidence and achievement motivation among international and junior national, international and sub-junior national, senior and sub-junior national male badminton players.

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